

THE KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE AND PRACTICES AMONG EMPLOYEES OF FOUNDATION UNIVERSITY ON SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11243017>

ABSTRACT

This study investigated solid waste management (SWM) during the COVID-19 pandemic at Foundation University (F.U.). The study aimed to cultivate a strong culture of responsible solid waste management within the academic community and develop effective policies and mechanisms to minimize waste generation on campus. The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. Using a validated self-made questionnaire, 40 respondents from 34 offices responded to the survey. Data collected were tabulated and subjected to various statistical analyses such as mean, weighted mean, and Spearman's rank coefficient. Notably, F.U. employees demonstrated above-average SWM knowledge regarding reuse, recycling, bin labeling, and responsible plastic bag use. Their attitudes towards SWM were similarly positive, valuing a clean environment, supporting university programs, and acknowledging the recycling of plastics. Furthermore, employees displayed a high proficiency in waste disposal and segregation within designated bins. Interestingly, a moderate, inverse relationship ($r_s = -0.315$; $p = 0.047 > 0.05$) emerged between SWM knowledge and attitude, indicating potentially more vital positive attitudes despite lower knowledge levels. Conversely, a strong, positive relationship ($r_s = 0.633$; $p = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$) linked attitude to practices, highlighting the critical role of positive attitudes in driving responsible waste segregation. However, no significant relationship ($r_s = -0.133$; $p = 0.417 > \alpha = 0.05$) was found between knowledge and practices, suggesting that knowledge alone may not directly influence individual waste management actions. Based on these findings, the study

recommends continued information dissemination, engaging awareness campaigns, and further research to strengthen F.U.'s SWM program and promote responsible practices within its community.

Keywords: *solid waste, Solid Waste Management, Knowledge, Attitude, Practice*

INTRODUCTION

Solid waste dumps are damaging the local ecology. According to the Compendium of the World Health Organization (WHO) and other U.N. guidance on health and the environment (2022), annual municipal solid waste exceeds 2 billion tons. Moreover, incorrect handling of these wastes can lead to various outcomes that could affect human health. Solid waste contaminates both land and bodies of water, disrupting the natural ecosystem. The WHO (2022) defined *solid waste* as “any type of garbage, trash, refuse, or discarded material.” Solid waste can originate from various sources, such as homes, businesses, industries, and educational institutions (Madrigal & Oracion, 2018).

Solid waste generation is a prevailing problem in the Philippines that will keep increasing as long as the population keeps growing (de Paz et al., 2020). According to the National SWM Report (2008-2018) submitted by the Department of Environment and Natural Resources, the nation's annual garbage production will rise from 13.48 million tons in 2010 to 14.66 million tons in 2014 and then to 18.05 million tons in 2020. In a news article by Mayuga, J. L. (2021), the Philippines produces garbage far beyond its capacity of over 21 million metric tons yearly. Even in the City of Dumaguete alone, in a study conducted by Saguban, L. E. (2020), several areas of improvement are identified, including insufficient enforcement of source segregation, limited truck units, shortage of garbage collectors, and the lack of community involvement. These factors and the city's small land area pose ongoing challenges to effective solid waste management.

The Philippine government enacted the Ecological Solid Waste Management Act of 2000, Republic Act (R.A.) 9003, to address this ever-growing environmental issue. In addition to the institutional mechanisms and strategies for the nation's SWM program's successful implementation, the law establishes the legal framework for a "systematic, comprehensive, and ecological SWM program that will ensure the protection of public health and the environment" (Madrigal & Oracion, 2018). Romualdo, A. Q. et al. (2022) demonstrate the practical application of R.A. 9003. It shows that schools in General Santos City (both public and private), crucial in shaping environmental awareness and behavior, are actively implementing and integrating SWM practices to a great extent.

In response to the relevant law and the University's commitment to environmental responsibility by initiating its very own Solid Waste Management System (SWMS), the researchers focus the study on two key areas: gauging the SWM awareness, attitude, and practices of faculty and staff. By delving into these aspects,

the researchers hope to achieve two goals: cultivating a strong culture of responsible waste management within the academic community and developing effective policies and mechanisms that minimize waste generation on campus.

Research Questions

This study examines Foundation University employees' Knowledge, Attitude, and practice levels regarding Solid Waste Management.

Specifically, the study would like to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practices of the Foundation University on waste management?
2. Is there a significant relationship between the F.U. personnel':
 - 2.1 knowledge and attitude;
 - 2.2 attitude and practices; and
 - 2.3 knowledge and practices?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study used a descriptive-correlational research design to describe the employees' knowledge, practice, and attitude toward solid waste management. The study directly correlated the level of knowledge among F.U. employees with their attitudes and practices. In addition, it also correlated the attitude toward Solid Waste Management with the practice among the employees at F.U.

Research Locale

The study involved employees from various offices of Foundation University in Dumaguete City, Negros Oriental, Philippines, a non-sectarian, non-profit private higher education institution. The University, founded on July 4, 1949, by Dr. Vicente G. Sinco, is renowned for its sustainability practices and eco-friendliness, having won the National Championship for the 2015 Search for Eco-friendly and Sustainable Schools.

Statistical Tools

The researchers analyzed the data using statistical tools such as mean, weighted mean, and Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient.

The researchers determined the level of Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice among Foundation University employees regarding solid waste management using the mean and Weighted Mean.

Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient was used to identify the degree of relationship between (a) knowledge versus attitude, (b) attitude versus practices, and (c) knowledge versus practices.

Research Respondents

The study encompassed all the different operational university offices during the pandemic. It included 27 offices on the main campus and seven on the north campus, totaling 34 offices in the study. The study had 40 respondents across these offices.

Research Instrument

The study utilized a self-made questionnaire that was validated and checked by three experts. The researchers conducted a dry run using Cronbach's alpha to assess the instrument's reliability and validity. Subsequently, the questionnaire was finalized and distributed to every department, where faculty and staff provided their responses.

Data Gathering Procedure and Analysis

The research adhered to the established protocol for data gathering. The Human Resources Department of the Foundation University approved the researchers' letter requesting permission to distribute questionnaires to faculty and staff in different offices. Faculty and staff received a consent letter explaining the critical elements of the study and the expectations as participants of the study. A consent form was attached to the letter, which F.U. participants signed if they agreed to participate and understood their role in the research.

The study spanned one month, with data collected weekly to assess the University's solid waste generation. The study measured faculty and staff's knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding waste management. Data collected were recorded, tabulated, and then subjected to various statistical analyses, including means and weighted means. The relationship between F.U. personnel's (a) knowledge and attitude, (b) knowledge and practices, and (c) attitude and practices were analyzed using the Spearman rank correlation coefficient.

RESULTS

Table 1. *Level of Knowledge of the FU Personnel on Waste Management (n =40)*

Indicator	Yes		No	
	f	%	f	%
True Statements				
1. Can plastic be reused and recycled?	40	100.00	0	0.00
2. Must garbage bins be properly labeled and tagged?	40	100.00	0	0.00
3. Is there an alternative way aside from using plastic bags when shopping?	40	100.00	0	0.00
4. Is improper management of garbage detrimental to health?	39	97.50	1	2.50
5. Is improper waste disposal a threat to the environment?	39	97.50	1	2.50
6. Can solid wastes be sorted?	38	95.00	2	5.00
7. Can biodegradable wastes be used in vermicomposting?	37	92.50	3	7.50
8. Do you know how to properly segregate the wastes?	37	92.50	3	7.50
9. Can waste be a resource?	36	90.00	4	10.00
10. Do you know about RA9003 or the solid waste management act?	31	77.50	9	22.50
11. Do you know the principle of waste characterization?	26	65.00	14	35.00
12. Do you know about Material Recovery Facility (MRF)?	25	62.50	15	37.50
13. Do you know the penalties for violation of solid waste management?	24	60.00	16	40.00
False Statements				
1. Tagging the garbage bag is optional.	12	30.00	28	70.00
2. Do you think open-fire burning of leaves, twigs, and other biodegradable waste is not harmful	10	25.00	30	75.00

to the environment?

3. Can face masks and other clinical wastes (expired medicine, bandages, used cotton) be disposed of together with other non-biodegradable waste?	8	20.00	32	80.00
4. Is sorting solid waste only achievable using a specialized machine?	7	17.50	33	82.50
5. Is throwing garbage in riverbanks, canals, seas and, etc. allowed?	5	12.50	35	87.50
6. Material Recovery Facility processed only food wastes.	4	10.00	36	90.00
7. Hazardous wastes are recyclable.	3	7.50	37	92.50

Mean = 17.08 (85.4% - Above Average)
sd = 2.44

Legend:	Rating	Verbal Description (VD)
	99% - 100%	Exceptional
	96% - 98%	Excellent
	93% -95%	Superior
	90% - 92%	Very Good
	87% - 89%	Good
	84% - 86%	Above Average
	81% - 83%	Average
	78% - 80%	Below Average
	75% - 77%	Passing

Table 1 presents the result on the level of knowledge among employees of the Foundation University on solid waste management.

Table 2. *Attitude of the FU Personnel on Waste Management (n =40)*

Indicators	$\bar{w\tilde{x}}$	Verbal Description	Attitude Interpretation
1. Having a clean environment is vital to health.	4.95	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
2. The solid waste management programs of the university shall be supported and participated from top to bottom of the organizational hierarchy.	4.93	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
3. I am aware that plastic can be recycled.	4.90	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
4. Implementation of the solid waste management act (RA9003) is very important in addressing problems with waste.	4.85	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
5. It is important that I should know the solid waste management policy and programs of the University.	4.85	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
6. It is necessary for me to practice reuse, recycle and reduce.	4.83	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
7. I am responsible of the university's wastes.	4.78	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
8. I play a very important role in minimizing the generation of wastes in school.	4.73	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
9. 10. Recycling should be an essential part of my way of life.	4.70	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
10. It concerns me if I see garbage scattered everywhere.	4.65	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
11. I am willing to know about environmental issues and concerns	4.65	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
12. I also have a role to minimize school and house waste.	4.63	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
13. I am committed to minimize waste.	4.60	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
14. I care for open-fire burning of wastes.	4.25	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
Composite	4.73	Strongly Agree	Very Positive

Legend	Scale	Verbal Description	Attitude Interpretation
	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very Positive
	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Positive
	2.61 – 3.40	Moderately Agree	Neutral
	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Negative

Table 2 stipulates the level of attitude among employees of the Foundation University on solid waste management.

Table 3. Practices of the FU Personnel on Waste Management (n =40)

Indicators	$w\bar{x}$	Verbal Description	Level of Practices
1. I clean and throw my garbage in the designated bins.	4.83	Always	Very High
2. I dispose of my garbage properly.	4.80	Always	Very High
3. I segregate biodegradable and non-biodegradable waste in a separate trash bin.	4.75	Always	Very High
4. I practice solid waste management in the office.	4.73	Always	Very High
5. I do not throw unused printed paper, instead I use the other side of the paper as a notepad.	4.63	Always	Very High
6. I do not throw garbage in canals, rivers, seas, and other bodies of water.	4.63	Always	Very High
7. I reuse plastic containers instead of throwing them right away after its empty.	4.56	Always	Very High
8. I properly labeled the garbage bag for easy and convenient pick up of the garbage collector.	4.40	Always	Very High
9. I bring my own food container to minimize the use of non-biodegradable materials.	4.15	Frequent	High
10. I don't burn both bio and non-biodegradable wastes.	4.15	Frequent	High
11. I use kitchen waste as compost.	3.93	Frequent	High
12. I used food leftovers as compost.	3.80	Frequent	High
13. I am using an Eco bag when buying foodstuffs and other basic and personal needs.	3.70	Frequent	High
Composite	4.39	Frequent	High
Legend	Scale	Verbal Description Level of Practices	
	4.21 – 5.00	Always	Very High
	3.41 – 4.20	Frequent	High
	2.61 – 3.40	Sometimes	Moderate
	1.81 – 2.60	Rare	Low
	1.00 – 1.80	Never	Very Low

Table 3 shows the level of practice among employees of the Foundation University in solid waste management.

Table 4. Relationship between Variables (n =40)

Variables		r_s	p-value	Decision	Remark
Knowledge versus Attitude		-0.315	0.047	Reject H_0	Significant
	Knowledge (Score) ($w\tilde{x}$)				Attitude
	10 – 13				4.98
	14 – 17				4.74
	18 – 20				4.67
Attitude versus Practices		0.633	0.000	Reject H_0	Significant
	Attitude ($w\tilde{x}$) ($w\tilde{x}$)				Practices
	3.84				≤ 4.43
	4.44 – 4.87				4.25
	4.88 – 5.00				4.76
Knowledge versus Practices		-0.133	0.417	Fail to reject H_0	Not significant

Level of significance = 0.05

Legend: Value of r Strength of Relationship (Statistical Correlation, 2009)
 Between ± 0.50 to ± 1.00 \pm strong relationship
 Between ± 0.30 to ± 0.49 \pm moderate relationship
 Between ± 0.10 to ± 0.29 \pm weak relationship
 Between ± 0.01 to ± 0.09 \pm very weak relationship

Table 4 depicts the relationship between knowledge and attitude, attitude and practices, and knowledge and practices.

DISCUSSION

The Level of Knowledge Among Employees of Foundation University on Solid Waste Management

Table 1 presents the level of knowledge about SWM among F.U. employees. The average knowledge was 85.4%, which resulted in above-average verbal description. The results showed that all university employees are aware of and have knowledge of the three indicators, mainly as follows: plastics can be reused and recycled, garbage bins must be appropriately labeled and tagged, and alternatives to using plastic bags when shopping, where the three indicators got a 100% response of "Yes." The next indicators followed were the detrimental impact on the health of improper garbage management and improper waste disposal as a threat to the environment. Both indicators got 97.50 percent of the "YES" response. The indicators on sorting of solid waste have a 95% response, biodegradable waste used in vermicomposting and the proper segregation of garbage both with 92.50%

response, and waste as a resource got a 90% response. Meanwhile, indicators about technicality, especially on laws about SWM and the other items covered by the law on SWM and its penalties for violation, got 70%, down to 60% of “Yes” responses about the knowledge aspect.

The constant reminder and the information dissemination campaign of the University’s waste segregation policy made the employees aware and mindful of the university policy on SWM regarding handling and managing their respective garbage and waste in every office.

Employees’ knowledge, especially on the 3Rs, is supported in a study by Tatlonghari and Jamias (2010), where the majority of the respondents know the importance of SWM concepts, including other environmental concepts like pollution, global warming due to the destruction of ozone layer where burning of trash was a contributory factor, and flooding– all effects of improper SWM. In addition, most respondents already knew important SWM concepts like the 3Rs (reducing, reusing, recycling) and segregating waste, such as what waste materials were biodegradable and non-biodegradable. Furthermore, Zakianis et al. (2017) presented that 93.7% of the household respondents have a good knowledge of waste management, and 85.7% care for the environment. Aside from that, in a study conducted by Omar et al. (2018) regarding the level of knowledge, most respondents have a good understanding of SWM.

Knowing that the University was recognized and awarded for its exemplary performance as a model university, being the Sustainable and Eco-Friendly School in Region VII and the entire Philippines in April 2016, the employees became knowledgeable about the University's SWM policy.

The Level of Attitude Among Employees of Foundation University on Solid Waste Management

Table 2 displays the attitude of F.U. personnel on Waste Management. The results show a very positive attitude of F.U. employees toward Waste Management. The respondents, based on items two, five, six, seven, eight, 12, and 13, strongly agree that waste production and management are the responsibilities of both the employees and the management.

This finding has shown that SWM is a significant concern and responsibility of F.U. personnel. The highly positive attitude greatly affected how people generated, handled, segregated, and even their interest in minimizing or reducing waste (Bowersox et al., 2005; Starovoytova & Namango, 2018). The researchers infer that the more people in the University feel responsible and have a positive attitude toward waste management, the better the outcome of waste management initiatives. Moreover, the study of Dung et al. (2017) supported the claims of College of Education students in the North Central Zone of Nigeria, whose attitude toward SWM was also positive.

The belief that waste management was the responsibility of employees and the university administration followed Bandura's social learning theory (as cited in

Simply Psychology, 2024). The social learning theory states explicitly that human social models, in this case, observing proper waste management in the University by all, can be very effective in influencing one to change behaviors, beliefs, or attitudes, as well as social and cognitive functioning. The observed attitude and practice influenced a positive attitude by most people.

Employees would observe the same practices when exposed to an environment that firmly observes proper waste management. The study of Starovoytova and Namango (2018) presented that 97% of respondents at Moi University in Kenya believed it was solely the administration's responsibility to keep the campus clean. Hence, the negative attitude toward waste management by students and the vendors inside the University contributed to the failure of SWM.

The Level of Practices Among Employees of Foundation University on Solid Waste Management

The resulting level of practices of Table 3 on Indicators One, two, three, four, five, six, seven, and eight were very high (4.21 – 5.00), with a verbal description of always. Meanwhile, the resulting level of practice for nine, 10, 11, 12, and 13 was High (3.41 – 4.20), with verbal descriptions of frequent. The composite value is 4.39, with a verbal description of frequent and a High level of practice. Positive SWM practices by F.U. personnel, as shown in Table 3.3, underscore the importance of worker awareness, as highlighted by Singh et al. (2021). This finding also aligns with Bautista (2019), who revealed that students engaged positively in proper SWM, focusing on waste disposal, recycling, and reuse practices. Moreover, Coker et al. (2016) argue that optimal waste management requires considering local social, economic, and cultural factors. Implementing effective practices based on these factors can help prevent injuries and infections.

The Relationship Between KAP Among Employees of Foundation University on Solid Waste Management

Table 4 shows the data for identifying the relationship between the different variables. Considering the knowledge and attitude of the personnel, the data revealed a negative rs-value (-0.315) and a p-value (0.047), which is lower than the level of significance (0.05). These findings mean a significant, inverse, and moderate relationship exists between the knowledge and attitude of the personnel on waste management. It signifies that employees have a lower knowledge of waste management.

While lacking in-depth knowledge of the regulations, Foundation University's staff showed an evident enthusiasm for practicing proper SWM on campus. Similarly, the study by Owojori et al. (2022) revealed that students' SWM knowledge was insufficient and lacking. However, the student's attitude was very positive, as they were ready to participate in recycling efforts. It also indicates a need for waste management education to enhance the knowledge of personnel at the University further. Madrigal and Oracion (2017) also emphasized that personnel, teachers, and the school should be crucial in educating, modeling, and persuading children to handle solid waste properly.

On the other hand, a significant, strong, and positive relationship ($r_s = 0.633$; $p = 0.000 < \alpha = 0.05$) exists between the attitude of the personnel and their practices on waste management. This finding connotes that personnel who acquire better attitudes toward waste management tend to display higher practices in waste segregation. The findings of Tatlonghari and Jamias (2010) show that many respondents accepted accountability in SWM. Their respondents claimed they typically made decisions and acted immediately without waiting for others to influence them in waste management. The result was also in line with the study of Johansson and Hedergard (2014), which states that segregating wastes reflects the attitude toward solid waste management.

Meanwhile, there is no significant relationship between the knowledge and the practices of the personnel on waste management ($r_s = -0.133$; $p = 0.417 > \alpha = 0.05$). The negative sign may mean an inverse relationship; however, the data are insufficient to indicate a significant relationship. This finding implies that the knowledge of the personnel cannot be considered a determinant of their practices. In other words, their knowledge cannot account for how the personnel manage waste segregation. This finding aligns with previous research (Molina & Catan, 2021), showing that students showed good waste practices but limited legal knowledge. Moreover, Rada et al. (2016) suggested that educational activities could improve the concerns school staff contribute to the total amount of waste generated in a region and the students' poor recycling practices in schools. Consequently, these findings prompted the need to increase awareness of the importance of information dissemination regarding waste management and its application of good recycling practices.

Conclusions

Based on the study's findings, the researchers concluded that the most considerable solid waste generated in F.U. was paper e during the pandemic, followed by plastic waste. It is also evident that the knowledge of the F.U. employees on SWM is above average, specifically on reuse, recycling, proper tagging and labeling of garbage bins, and the use of plastic bags when shopping. Additionally, their attitude towards SWM is very positive, specifically on the value of having a clean environment that is good for a person's health and gaining support for the University's SWM programs. Moreover, their SWM practice is high, particularly regarding the disposal and segregation of garbage in the designated bins. Interestingly, the study identified a moderate, inverse relationship between SWM knowledge and attitude. It suggests that personnel exhibited positive attitudes toward responsible waste management even with lower knowledge.

On the other hand, there was a strong, positive relationship between attitude and practices. It highlights the crucial role of positive attitudes in driving responsible waste segregation behavior. However, no significant relationship was established between knowledge and practices, indicating that knowledge alone may not be a determining factor in individual waste management actions.

Recommendations

Based on these findings, the researchers recommend continuous information dissemination about the SWM program, including relevant laws and regulations. Given the dynamic campus environment with new students and employees every year, it is essential. They also suggest engaging in awareness campaigns on proper SWM practices and conducting annual follow-up research. This follow-up research should include additional indicators assessing the relationship between SWM knowledge and practices. Furthermore, a comparative analysis that provides for pre-pandemic and post-pandemic comparisons would help understand changes in waste management behavior.

Future research could also investigate student inclusion to understand the University's waste management landscape comprehensively. Implementing these recommendations can further strengthen F.U.'s SWM program and promote responsible waste management practices within its community.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers conducted the study safely and ethically. The researchers assure the privacy and confidentiality of all the information gathered from the respondents. This study underwent review from the Office of the University Research Ethics Committee for review and compliance with the ethical standards. Only the researchers and F.U. employees could identify the information provided. The respondents were also well informed that the results would be presented in the research study and publicized. The University Research Ethics Committee also confirmed that the research is not harmful to the F.U. participants and certifies proper use of information. The researchers also ensured that the faculty and staff's contribution would be voluntary and that they could withdraw from the research at any time.

Acknowledgments

The authors thank Foundation University for allowing them to conduct this research and the faculty and staff for participating.

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